

Flood Mapping Using GeoAI and Aerial RGB Imagery

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Abstract

Floods increasingly threaten human populations, infrastructure, agriculture, and ecosystems, highlighting the need for accurate and timely flood mapping. While satellite-based remote sensing is widely used, limitations such as cloud cover, revisit time, and spatial resolution can reduce its effectiveness during flood events. This study presents a deep learning workflow for flood segmentation using high-resolution UAV RGB imagery acquired in Flanders, Belgium. A manually annotated dataset of 199 image tiles derived from UAV orthophotos was used to evaluate multiple architectures combining different pretrained backbones (Swin Transformer, OCEBO, CRIBO, and DINOv3) with a common UPerNet decoder, alongside a lightweight DINOv3 embedding-based SVC classifier. All tested approaches achieved strong performance, with F1-scores between 0.90 and 0.95. DINOv3 + UPerNet produced the best overall results, while DINOv3 + SVC demonstrated competitive accuracy with lower model complexity. The proposed workflow shows strong potential for accurate flood mapping in both rural and urban environments.

Keywords: flooding, deep learning, UAV, aerial imagery

1. Introduction

Flooding is a high-priority hazard due to the negative impacts it imposes on the environment, economy and population. The direct effects on humans vary from contamination of potable water and spread of waterborne diseases to injuries or even death. Infrastructure can be seriously damaged, causing people to get dislocated and public services to be interrupted. Flooding of agricultural zones can lead to crop yield reduction or destruction, loss of livestock, soil erosion, among others. When floods occur, ecosystems are disturbed and pollutants can spread. All these consequences of flooding are invariably accompanied by economic loss. Moreover, the frequency of floods around the globe is expected to increase as climate change progresses. In order to take effective measures to prevent and mitigate these impacts, insights into the

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occurrence and dynamics of floods are crucial. To do so, remote sensing is a widely used tool, as it allows to capture spatially continuous information over larger areas.

Many flood mapping methods employ spaceborne data. Multispectral sensors like Sentinel-2, Landsat and MODIS are valuable sources of data when dealing with flooding events (Albertini et al., 2022; Composto et al., 2025). However, these images often suffer from the presence of clouds, making Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery provided by satellites like Sentinel-1 an invaluable alternative. Where established approaches rely on traditional techniques like thresholding (Chini et al., 2017; Martinis et al., 2015), effective methods employing deep learning algorithms and/or foundation models for radar (Sharma & Saharia, 2025; Wu et al., 2023) or combined optical-radar data have been proposed in the literature (Bai et al., 2021; Kostejn et al., 2025; Sekine et al., 2024). However, despite the quality of the derived flood maps, satellite imagery suffers from various limitations that reduce its practical applicability when a flood occurs: temporal coverage - overpass times might not coincide with the flood event; spatial resolution - often, the large spatial coverage of satellite data comes at the cost of lower spatial resolution; environmental conditions impeding the acquisition of useful data - presence of clouds in the case of optical sensors; natural configuration of the scene – flooded vegetated areas are harder to observe by SAR imagery due to the high signal scattering of the vegetation.

Given the above limitations related to satellite imagery, exploiting images acquired by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) becomes a valuable alternative. UAV flights can be planned and performed more easily, and can mitigate some challenges encountered in satellite data, e.g. the presence of clouds. Furthermore, modern UAVs can cover large areas, and the acquired images have high spatial resolution, increasing the interpretability of the derived maps and the applicability for urban zones.

The fast development of deep learning architectures and foundation models for GeoAI constitutes both an opportunity to aim for higher quality maps and a challenge to find a fine balance between architecture complexity, efficiency and accuracy. Advanced works employ deep learning algorithms such as fully convolutional neural networks (Gebrehiwot et al., 2019), foundation models in combination with semantic segmentation architectures (Deb & Verma, 2025), unsupervised deep learning (Simantiris & Panagiotakis, 2025) and transformer-based architectures (Shaheen et al., 2025), among others. In this work, we complement these works by presenting a workflow for flood mapping using RGB aerial images.

2. Methodology

Our approach falls under the category of supervised deep learning methods. A training dataset is curated by hand-labeling publicly available images of floods in Flanders, Belgium. Then, we exploit the modular structure of deep learning architectures to build various networks composed of different backbone types and one common decoding head. We also add one architecture composed of a foundation model backbone and a machine learning algorithm applied to data embeddings, for comparison purposes.

The training images were selected from a large dataset of 171 UAV orthophotos acquired by the Flemish Environment Agency over 46 sites on 29 different dates in the period 2019-2023. A set

of 199 tiles of 1024x1024 pixels were sampled from 54 of the 171 available drone images and manually annotated, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Example of annotated tile. The ground-truth flooding mask is shown in orange.

The proposed workflow exploits the modular characteristic of deep learning architectures. On the one hand, we use an encoder-decoder approach in which one common decoding head is placed on top of various feature extractors or encoders used as the backbone. This allows for comparisons on the efficiency of the various encoding techniques to tackle the flood segmentation task. On the other hand, embeddings derived from a recently released foundation model are directly employed and fed to a well-established machine learning algorithm. This type of approach does not need retraining or fine-tuning and the goal is to observe if it can constitute an alternative to the first approach. Below, we list the different architectures tested in our workflow:

- 1) **Swin transformer + UPerNet:** The Swin transformer (Shifted Window Transformer) (Liu et al., 2021) is a widely used computer vision backbone used in a variety of tasks such as image classification, object detection and semantic segmentation. The UPerNet (Unified Perceptual Parsing Network) (Xiao et al., 2018) decoder employing multi-scale feature extraction and global context is largely used in semantic segmentation tasks.
- 2) **OCEBO + UPerNet:** OCEBO (Object-Centric Pretraining by Target Encoder Bootstrapping) (Đukić et al., 2025) is mostly used for object-centric pretraining in computer vision and is competitive to other models trained on much larger datasets.
- 3) **CRIBO + UPerNet:** CRIBO (Cross-Image Object Level Bootstrapping) (Lebailly et al., 2023) is a self-supervised learning method designed to learn dense object-centric representations, rather than just global image features.
- 4) **DINOv3 + UPerNet:** DINOv3 (Distillation with No Labels v3) (Siméoni et al., 2025) is a self-supervised vision foundation model, pretrained with both natural and satellite imagery. Different variants are available, from heavy models to light distilled ones. It

provides dense visual representations as patch embeddings learned in a self-supervised manner.

- 5) **DINOv3 + SVC**: SVC (Support Vector Classification) (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995) is a supervised learning algorithm based on Support Vector Machines, designed for binary or multi-class classification tasks.

To summarize, the network instances implemented in our workflow cover the following variable components:

- Backbone – we use one general-purpose feature extractor (Swin transformer), two object-centric feature extractors (OCEBO and CRIBO) and one foundation model (DINOv3)
- Decoder – we employ UPerNet as a common decoder in all configurations except for the last one where SVC computes the flooding map on top of DINOv3 embeddings. Note that, when embeddings are input to machine learning algorithms, the spatial resolution of the output map is degraded in comparison to the input images, according to the patch size of the embeddings.

For an objective comparison of the tested architectures, the following performance metrics were computed for the validation dataset:

- Precision (P): proportion of predicted positive instances that are truly positive. It quantifies the classifier's ability to avoid false positives by measuring correctness among positive predictions.
- Recall (R): proportion of actual positive instances correctly identified. It quantifies sensitivity, emphasizing how well the model captures all true positives while minimizing false negatives.
- F1-score (F1): harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single balanced metric. It penalizes extreme imbalance between precision and recall.
- Mean Intersection Over Union (mIOU): ratio of the intersection area to the union area between predicted and ground truth regions (reported as a mean across the target classes).

3. Results

Figure 2 shows examples of flooding maps derived by three of the proposed architectures over a flooded area, and Figure 3 provides a zoomed-in view over flooded areas in both rural and urban environments in another region. The figures reveal good performance of all architectures, but also some differences between the produced maps.

a) RGB image

b) Flood map: Swin transformer + UPerNet

c) OCEBO + UPerNet

d) DINOv3 + SVC

Figure 2. Examples of flood maps derived by different architectures implemented in the proposed workflow.

Figure 3. Model output (logits) by architecture #1 (Swin+UPerNet) over one of the images, zoom-in over flooded areas (rural at the left; urban at the right).

In Figure 4, the four metrics are plotted w.r.t. the binarization threshold applied. Note that DINOv3+UPerNet is overall superior to the other architectures. The ML classification applied to the DINOv3 foundation model embeddings also exhibits competitive performance to OCEBO + UPerNet in terms of F1 and mIoU, despite relying on a smaller number of tunable internal parameters and lower effective spatial resolution, due to the embedding strategy applied by DINOv3. SWIN + UPerNet performs similarly at lower thresholds but shows a stronger decrease in recall, F1, and mIoU at higher thresholds. CRIBO + UPerNet remains slightly below OCEBO and DINOv3 + SVC in F1 and mIoU across most thresholds.

Figure 4. Accuracy comparison over the considered architectures, including sensitivity to the binarization threshold.

4. Conclusion and outlook

In this study, a range of pretrained (self-supervised or ImageNet) backbones were connected to a UPerNet decoder and trained for flood segmentation on UAV-acquired RGB images. In addition, an SVC was trained on DINOv3 embeddings. All setups perform very good, with F1 scores between 0.9 and 0.95, though the DINOv3 + UPerNet performs best. A qualitative analysis of the results shows the models perform very good in both rural and urban areas.

The results presented in this paper offer a wide range of possibilities for future investigations. The models here are compared strictly based on their accuracy, but other factors will be

considered in future work: the number of parameters required by each architecture will be analyzed for a better understanding of strengths and limitations, the runs will be repeated for multiple seeds in order to assess stochastic variability, the impact of spatial resolution and training patch size will be investigated, and model transferability and applicability to other data domains will be assessed.

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